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An Analysis of Students' Participation in Secondary, Higher Secondary, and Higher Education in India

Mohammed Imran*, Sabina Begum** and Alok Ranjan Behera***

*PhD Scholar, ICSSR Doctoral Fellow, School of Women's Studies, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha

**Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Analytical and Applied Economics, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha

***Assistant Professor, Department of Analytical and Applied Economics, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the multifaceted role of education, particularly focusing on youth participation, transition rates, dropout rates, and retention rates in the Indian education system. Drawing upon the Capability Approach, UNESCO's post-2015 development agenda, and various scholarly works, the paper underscores education's pivotal function in fostering fundamental learning outcomes, enhancing substantive freedom, and promoting global citizenship. It reviews literature highlighting the importance of students' participation in decision-making processes, the impact of youth-led initiatives, and the potential of digital technology in education. Additionally, the paper provides an analysis of secondary data obtained from the Ministry of Education and other sources, examining transition rates, dropout rates, and retention rates across different levels of education in India. It identifies challenges and disparities in educational access and attainment, particularly among marginalized communities and across states. Despite progress in enrolment rates, significant dropout rates persist, reflecting ongoing challenges in the education system. The paper concludes by emphasizing the importance of addressing barriers to youth participation and ensuring equitable access to quality education for all, in line with national and global development goals.

KEYWORDS: Education, Youth participation, Transition rates, Dropout rates, Retention rates

INTRODUCTION

In terms of improving, one's life chances and opening up countless opportunities, education is invaluable. Evident are the many and varied educational obligations of the Capability Approach. Education is often called a foundation for other abilities because it helps students master a distinct set of core skills (Azam & Kingdon, 2011). Education also gives people more real choices, which means more substantive freedom, to live the lives they choose to live. Education is both a means to an end—the realisation of one's life choices—and an effect on one's life possibilities. The process of capability-enabling can inculcate both hard and soft abilities, as teaching, learning, and human growth are closely related. In essence, education enables its recipients to

Mohammed Imran, PhD Scholar, ICSSR Doctoral Fellow,
School of Women's Studies, Utkal University,
Bhubaneswar, Odisha, 751004,
E-Mail: imran75044@gmail.com,
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-1615-3528>

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develop abilities that facilitate critical and creative thinking, problem-solving, making well-informed decisions, handling and adapting to new situations, and communicating effectively. The goal of education should be to help students develop their skills by providing them with high-quality resources, methods, and settings in which to study (Chandrasekhar & Sharma, 2014).

UNESCO emphasises the importance of a well-defined and publicly-stated education development objective for the years after 2015. The main Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aim to alleviate poverty, promote democracy and peace, and encourage global citizenship; all of which depend on education. Investments like this are crucial if India's youth are to achieve the SDGs' aims of providing adequate education (Goal 4) and decent work (Goal 8). Public funding for education must be sufficient if educational systems are to be fair and successful in achieving the SDGs.

The key to creating welcoming and productive classrooms is getting young people involved. Participatory pedagogy encourages youth participation in a range of educational pursuits and gives them a voice in decisions that impact their education. Key results and perspectives on youth involvement in education are highlighted in the following literature study. The effects of student input on school policymaking are investigated by Mitra and Serriere (2012). It demonstrates how a more pleasant school climate and better learning results may be achieved when youth are involved in creating educational policies and procedures. Young people need to be able to express themselves and have a say in school governance, according to the study. To find and fix the reasons for educational inequality, it is important to involve disadvantaged youth in decision-making processes, as discussed in the role of youth participation in addressing educational inequalities. Along with previous research (Pal & Ghosh, 2007; Mitra & Serriere, 2012; YDR, 2017), this study highlights the importance of empowering young people to make a difference in their communities. Learn about youth-driven programs that have improved educational environments and how they have empowered youth in education through youth-led initiatives. The study emphasises the significance of teaching young people leadership skills so they may actively participate in creating their own educational experiences (Ho et al., 2015; Collura et al., 2019). There are both possibilities and challenges for youth involvement in schooling. The literary works discuss the benefits and challenges that young people face when they are enrolled in school. Institutional reluctance, a

dearth of adult support, and inadequate resources are all mentioned as potential obstacles. Research by Mooji and Dev (2001) and Mitra and Serriere (2012) examines the potential benefits of student participation and youth voices in educational decision-making. How might digital technology enhance youth engagement in education? That is the question Ilomaki and Lakkala (2018) want to answer. The article explores the use of social media, virtual collaboration tools, and online platforms to engage youth in educational activities. Potential problems and hazards associated with digital technology use are also covered in the paper.

To sum up, youth participation in education is an important and multi-faceted idea that helps to make classrooms more welcoming and productive for all students. Students' personal growth, leadership abilities, and feelings of ownership over their education are all positively impacted when teachers encourage active participation from students. Nevertheless, to guarantee that every young person has an equal chance to participate significantly in education, it is crucial to resolve the difficulties and obstacles that can prevent youth involvement. The paper analyses students' transition rates, drop-out rates, and retention rates in secondary, higher secondary, and higher education in India.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Selected Educational Statistics, UDISE, UDISE+, and All India Survey of Higher Education are some of the publications produced by the Ministry of Education that provide the secondary data used in this study. Also included are supplemental data sets from various sources, including PLFS and the Economic Surveys of India. This study made use of descriptive statistics.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The Indian Educational System

The cycle of secondary schooling now encompasses both the secondary and senior secondary sub-levels. Each secondary education sub-level has exams administered by national or state examination boards. These kids fall into the 14 to 17-year-old age range. There are two methods to receive a vocational education: as a senior high school elective and through the Indian Institutes of Industrial Training and Polytechnics. To apply for higher education, students must pass the senior secondary exams. However, only a strong academic record, as demonstrated by the grades earned, aids pupils in getting accepted into higher education institutions.

In India, students go through a three-tiered educational system that begins with primary school and continues through college. Following the implementation of NEP in 2020, there are three levels of elementary education: Middle (ages 11–14), Preparatory (ages 8–11), and Foundational (ages 3–8). Before that, there were two levels of elementary education: primary education, which covers students aged 6–10, and upper primary education, which covers students aged 11–13. The implementation of a “no detention policy” extended to primary schools (Table 1).

Table 1. The New Education Policy and Its Impact on India's Educational System

Levels	Existing Age (years)	New Structure NEP Age (Years)	Levels
Higher Education	18-23	Flexible	Higher Edu.
Senior Secondary	17-18	14-18	Secondary
Secondary	15-16	11-14	Middle
Upper Primary	11-14	8-11	Preparatory
Primary	6-10	3-8	Foundation
Pre-Primary	5	-	-

Source: Developed based on NEP, 1986 and NEP, 2020.

The Indian higher education system is structured hierarchically, with universities, research institutions, and deemed-to-be universities at the top, followed by discipline-specific colleges and professional institutions. Undergraduate programs are generally categorized into non-professional courses (arts, science, and commerce) lasting three years, and PHE (medicine, engineering, law, and education) varying from 2 to 6 years. All lead to bachelor's degrees. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 has introduced flexibility in learning pathways, allowing multiple entry and exit points and credit transfers across institutions, both domestically and internationally. Additionally, open universities provide an alternative to the regular system. The official age range for higher education in India is 18 to 23 years. This structure aims to provide diverse educational opportunities and pathways for students pursuing higher education in India.

Engaging Students in the Learning Process

When compared to elementary and secondary school, higher education for young people has a far greater impact on economic growth, redistribution, and poverty reduction. Because young people with secondary

education are more open to training to meet the needs of globalized local markets, they are in great demand in today's tech-savvy, knowledge-driven international economy. The reason behind this is that secondary education plays a vital role in preparing young people for careers in the modern economy. It does this by exposing them to abstract problem-solving techniques, critical thinking, and formal reasoning, as well as occupationally relevant content (Lewin and Caillods, 2001). Strengthening system capacity and quality, encouraging skill development, and promoting lifelong learning are all goals of the National Youth Policy (2014). Achieving these two goals relies heavily on youth education.

As a measure of educational progress, the Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) shows how much diversity there is across different grade levels. Table 2 shows that between 2004–05 and 2019–20, the GER at the secondary level rose from 51.7 per cent to 78.7 per cent. From 2004–05 to 2019–20, the equivalent increase was a more modest 28–51 per cent at the higher secondary level. There has been a positive shift in the previous 30 years, with gender gaps in GERs decreasing across all educational levels. Nevertheless, by 2030, the goal of the NEP, 2020, is to ensure that all individuals participate in formal education. What this means is that by 2030 (NEP 2020), all school curricula must incorporate GER. As of 2019–20, it's worth noting that just half of the children enrolled in school get coverage.

In order to accomplish this goal, there are a number of critical obstacles. Numerous factors impact both the real learning and the successful completion of schooling. Levels of involvement in school education are impacted by these factors, which in turn affect both the demand for education in society and the quality of educational resources and results. These factors include (i) issues of poverty, economic disparity, and other forms of systemic inequality; (ii) greater individual expenditure on enrolling in a course of study; (iii) imbalance of knowledge; (iv) socially and physically stratified access to educational opportunities; (v) education's poor scholastic performance; (vi) the expanding role and magnitude of the commercial sector; (vii) government spending on education has seen relatively little growth; (viii) elements about the system, including matters concerning teacher responsibility; and (ix) a probable slowdown in economic growth shortly as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic, with far-reaching consequences for children's education and a major influence on government spending on social services.

Table 2. Gross Enrolment Ratio in the Academic Environment

Years	Secondary			Higher Secondary			Higher Education		
	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total
2004-05	57.4	45.3	51.7	30.8	24.5	27.8	11.6	8.2	10.0
2005-06	57.6	46.2	52.2	31.4	25.2	28.5	13.5	9.4	11.6
2010-11	69.2	60.9	65.2	42.3	36.2	39.4	20.8	17.9	19.4
2011-12	69.0	63.9	66.6	47.6	43.9	45.9	22.1	19.4	20.8
2012-13	67.9	67.4	67.7	43.9	43.2	43.6	22.3	19.8	21.1
2014-15	76.4	77.5	76.9	52.5	52.6	52.5	24.5	22.7	23.6
2015-16	78.6	80.1	79.3	55.4	56.1	55.7	25.4	23.5	24.5
2016-17	78.5	80.3	79.3	51.1	51.7	51.4	26.0	24.5	25.2
2019-20	78.9	78.4	78.7	50.5	52.4	51.4	26.9	27.3	27.1

Source: Education in India; Selected Educational Statistics, UDISE+

From 2004–05 to 2019–20, the GER in universities jumped substantially, rising from 10 per cent to nearly 27 per cent (Table 2). Despite this, GER has been improving in institutions of higher learning. Additionally, the trend shows that between 25 and 30 percent of students drop out of school at every grade level. The NEP 2020 also calls for increasing the GER to half by 2035, which would greatly increase access to higher education. Higher education has been propelled forward by this change in emphasis, which is significant for the expanding worldwide economy that has increased the demand for trained workers.

Male and female educational attainment levels in rural and urban areas are shown in the bar chart. It divides the people into four groups based on their degree of education: illiterate, elementary school, middle school, and high school. Among men living in rural areas, 5.9 per cent are illiterate, 12.8 per cent have completed elementary school, 28.7 per cent have completed middle school, and 52.6 per cent have completed high school or above. In rural areas, 11.5 per cent of women cannot read or write; 15.5 per cent have completed elementary school; 26.4 per cent have completed some college; and 46.6 per cent have completed high school or more. As for men living in urban areas, just 3.5 per cent are illiterate, 8.9 per cent have completed elementary school,

20.9 per cent have completed middle school, and 66.8 per cent have completed high school or higher. Among urban women, 5.4 per cent are illiterate, 8.6 per cent have completed elementary school, 19 per cent have completed middle school, and 66.9 per cent have completed high school or higher. As contrast to rural areas, urban areas have a higher percentage of people with a secondary education or above; moreover, urban females make up the largest portion of this category. The reverse is true: the proportion of the population with lower levels of education is larger in rural areas (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of Persons Aged 15–29 years by Highest Level of Successfully Completed Education (in percentage) between 2017–18 (PLFS I) and 2018–19 (PLFS II)

Source: PLFS II, 2018-19

Dropouts among students

The dropout rate measures the percentage of students or participants who leave or disengage from a program, course, or organization before completing it. It is a negative indicator and reflects the rate at which individuals are unable or unwilling to continue their involvement.

$$\text{Dropout Rate} = \frac{\text{[(Number of students/ members who leave or disengage)]}}{\text{(Initial number of students)} * 100}$$

Figure 2. Primary Education Drop-Out Rate
Source: UDISE+, Educational Statistics

Figure 3. Upper Primary Education Drop-Out Rate
Source: UDISE+, Educational Statistics

Figure 4. Secondary Education Drop-Out Rate
Source: UDISE+, Educational Statistics

There are various issues with the Indian educational system. Preventing school drop-outs throughout young people's crucial learning phases is the largest difficulty. Millions of students are forced by the high dropout rate to face adulthood without the basic skills necessary to support themselves. Educators in India are facing a

learning crisis across the board. Despite attending school, millions of students fail to acquire basic skills (ASER Reports, various difficulties).

The dropout rates generally show a decreasing trend over the years for all levels of education from 2013-14 to 2021-22. In most cases, the dropout rates for girls are lower than those for boys, suggesting that girls tend to stay in school more consistently. There are fluctuations in dropout rates from year to year, which could be influenced by various factors, including changes in educational policies, economic conditions, and societal factors. The dropout rates for 2020-21 show a mixed pattern, with some levels experiencing a slight increase, particularly at the upper primary level. This could be a result of the disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic on education.

The secondary level has experienced the most significant improvement, with a notable decrease in dropout rates. The primary level has also seen a substantial decrease in dropout rates, but there has been a slight increase in recent years. The upper primary level, while fluctuating, has shown some improvement over the years. This data indicates progress in reducing dropout rates, which is a positive sign for education. However, it is essential to continue implementing effective policies and interventions to further decrease dropout rates and ensure that all children have access to quality education and complete their schooling successfully (Figures 2, 3, 4).

Transition Rates

One such sign of a capability-enhancing process besides dropout rates is transition rates. The percentage of first-year students who go on to the following grade level is what it indicates. How many elementary school pupils go on to enroll in secondary school is shown by the transition rates in this study. How many elementary school pupils go on to enroll in secondary school is shown by the transition rates in this study. In addition to the quality and performance at the primary levels of education, the extent to which students move to secondary school is an indicator of the demand for secondary education. Formal secondary education is the most effective way to build life and work skills. The expansion of elementary schools over the last decade has led to an increase in the number of pupils enrolling in secondary schools. Grade 8 to 9 enrolment rates have jumped from 81.4 per cent to 95.6 per cent in the last 20 years, showing a considerable improvement, especially

for female students. To achieve the goal of universalizing education set by NEP 2020, there is still room for improvement in the transition from Grade X to Grade XI, despite a constant and good trend over time. The successful transfer rates from high school to college are yet another indicator that has been considered in this context. From 64.7 per cent in 2005–06 to 85.7 per cent in 2018–19, this demonstrated an improvement (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Transition Rates across Levels of Education in India

Source: Educational Statistics, Ministry of Education

From 2000-01 to 2018-19, the bar graph tracks three transitions: elementary to secondary (green bars), secondary to senior secondary (blue bars), and senior secondary to higher education (yellow bars). It also shows the transition rates (TR) across various educational levels in a specific area. The overall improvement in the progression to secondary education is indicated by the peak transition rate from elementary to secondary school in 2018–19, which reached 95.6 per cent. From 46.1 per cent in 2000-01 to 69.6 per cent in 2018-19, the transition rate from secondary to senior secondary school has been steadily increasing, albeit it does fluctuate. With a high of 87.4 per cent in 2010–2012 and a recent levelling off at 85–86 per cent, the percentage of seniors who continue their education after high school varies widely. All levels of educational transitions seem to have gotten better throughout the course of the observed time, according to the statistics (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Transition Rate

Source: Educational Statistics, Ministry of Education

Retention Rate in secondary education

The retention rate refers to the percentage of students or participants who continue to be enrolled or engaged in a program, course, or organization over a specific period.

$$RR = \left[\frac{\text{Number of students/ Members who remain enrolled or engaged}}{\text{Initial number of students}} \right] * 100$$

Figure 7. Retention Rate

Source: UDISE and UDISE+

The retention rate has fluctuated over the years but generally shows a slightly positive trend. In 2014-15, the retention rate was 57.24 per cent and in 2021-22, it reached 64.7 per cent. The fluctuations in retention rate may suggest variations in factors influencing student retention, such as teaching quality, learning environment, or socio-economic conditions.

The GER and RR do not follow an identical pattern. While the GER increases consistently, the RR showed fluctuations with a positive overall trend. The retention rate tends to be lower than the enrolment rate, indicating that some students might not continue their education after enrolling in secondary schools. The difference between the GER and RR indicates that there is a dropout rate in the system (Figure 7).

CONCLUSION

The secondary level has experienced the most significant improvement, with a notable decrease in dropout rates. The primary level has also seen a substantial decrease in dropout rates, but there has been a slight increase in recent years. The upper primary level, while showing a fluctuation, has shown marginal improvement over the years. Data indicates progress in reduction in dropout rates, which is a positive sign for the status of education in the country. The data shows rising rates of progression from elementary to secondary and from senior secondary to higher education, suggesting that there have been good advancements in educational transitions over time. The retention rate has fluctuated over the years but generally shows a slightly positive trend.

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MI, SB & ARB was responsible for the first manuscript draft. All authors contributed to subsequent drafts and approved the final version.

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